

INCREASING THE OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF PASSENGER CARS USING SYNTHETIC GAS FUELS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842268>

Abstract: The main efficiency indicators of increasing the performance of passenger cars using synthetic gas fuels and the use of compressed and liquefied gases in cars are presented. In order to reduce the negative impact of cars on the environment, the use of gas fuels can improve environmental performance, extend the engine's efficiency and service life, maintain the condition of parts for a long time, and achieve a number of other positive indicators.

Key words: transport, car, liquefied and compressed gas, gas cylinder, operational, natural gas, gasoline, diesel, engine.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan is one of the few car-producing countries. Today, reliable, convenient and safe vehicles for light and passenger transport, which are filling the streets of our country, are making people's distance closer and their problems easier. The consistent application of modern technologies to the industry, the acceleration of modernization work, makes it possible to produce motor vehicles that meet world standards.

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 10, 2007 "On the development of gas filling stations for cars and gas filling stations for cars and measures for the gradual transition of vehicles to liquefied and compressed gas" the works carried out on the basis of it are bearing fruit.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

A gas cylinder car is a car that runs on compressed or liquefied combustible gases, gas cylinders are installed on the chassis of the car, sometimes on top. Natural gas, gas from oil refining and extraction, and coke gas from coal recycling are compressed. Methane gas is pumped into the compressed gas cylinder with a pressure of up to 20 MPa. Liquefied gases: propane-butane and propylene-butylene are liquefied at normal temperature and pumped into cylinders with a pressure of 1.6 MPa; liquefied methane gas is liquefied at atmospheric pressure and a temperature of -161.3° and pumped into isothermal cylinders with a pressure of 1 MPa. The advantage of a car with a gas cylinder over cars running on liquid fuel is that it eats less engine parts, it is possible to increase the engine power due to increasing the compression level, it saves fuel, and the toxicity of the gases coming out of the engine is reduced.

Nowadays, exhaust gases from vehicles are the main source of atmospheric air pollution. In order to reduce the harmful gases emitted by vehicles, it is necessary to carry out an environmental inspection of vehicles once a quarter. During the environmental inspection, the amount of gases emitted by vehicles is checked and diagnosed with the help of gas-smoke measuring devices. Our department has a diagnostic point equipped with the necessary gas and smoke measuring devices. In cases where the amount of smoke and gas is found to be higher than the specified standards, vehicles are allowed to be used only after they are diagnosed and repaired.

RESULTS

The car fleet of the Republic of Uzbekistan is constantly being filled with new models of domestic and foreign buses, trucks and cars. In order to increase the competitiveness of cars produced in the automotive industry of our republic, it is necessary to improve the design of cars and their operational characteristics, to improve the operation of alternative energy sources. In addition, the conversion of cars to compressed and liquefied gas fuel, the use of polymer and composite materials also fully meets the standards of fuel economy. The use of polymer and composite materials in the construction of cars produced in our country (mainly in the body and cabin part), the most important of which is the transfer to compressed and liquefied gas fuel, has a positive effect on a number of environmental indicators.

This is achieved for the following reasons:

1. Improvement of the composition of the combustible mixture and combustion processes;
2. Improvement of fuel transmission and ignition systems;
3. The use of an electronic system that controls the operation of the engine, an exhaust gas neutralizer, and a system that captures gasoline vapors. The most effective ways to improve the structure of gasoline cars are:
 - recirculation of waste gases (NO_x content is reduced by 40-60%) and use of a two-component catalytic neutralizer (CO and C_xH_y content is reduced by 75-90%);
 - control of fuel injection into the intake manifold (reduces the toxicity of waste gases by 25-30%);
 - application of a computer system that controls work processes and waste gases, including dosed spraying, electronic control system and three-component neutralizer;
 - multi-valve engine cylinder injection control (the charge acts as a lump and exhaust gas toxicity meets EURO 3 standards - CO up to 2.3 g/km C_xH_y up to 0.2...0.3 g/km);
 - control of standard indicators of gasoline due to the use of carbon almond sorbents (evaporation of light hydrocarbons from gasoline is reduced by 85-95%). In diesel cars;
 - turbocharger and intermediate air cooling (NO_x and solid particles are reduced up to 30%);
 - Use of a catalyst oxidizing exhaust gas neutralizer together with a start neutralizer (CO -85-95, C_xH_y -75 -80, NO_x is reduced by 20%);
 - increase the injection pressure to 18...20 MPA and control it electronically (fuel turns into very small particles, burns quickly and completely, solid particles are reduced by 40-60%).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of gasoline and diesel fuels in car engines is considered a great harm to the environment and people, it causes great operational and environmental problems due to the release of toxic gases, engine overheating, and in order to solve these problems, alternative energy sources are pressed into cars. and the use of liquefied gas fuels provides many effective results. The use of gas fuel in cars is used as an ecologically clean fuel for the environment, ensuring long-term operation of the engine.

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